

MAIN FEATURES OF USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PHYSICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOL

Hamdamov Begali Isroilovich

Jizzax State Pedagogical University

4 Sharof Rashidov, Jizzax 130100, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14173253>

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the relevance of using information technologies in teaching physics to enhance students' cognitive and mental activity. The article considers the features of using a computer in the educational process. The use of computer technologies allows organizing students' independent cognitive work to study the phenomena of the surrounding reality. There are different options for organizing students' work: conducting research under the guidance and according to the teacher's instructions; students can be asked to independently put forward hypotheses, and conduct research according to the plan proposed by the teacher. An option is possible in which students themselves draw up a research plan, implement it and draw conclusions. In this case, the reproductive method of teaching is replaced by independent acquisition of knowledge based on the implementation of experimental and research activities, leading the student (with the appropriate methodology) to an independent discovery of the studied pattern.*

Keywords: *electronic educational resources; physics catalog; mathematics; computer science; development of research skills; computer; computer demonstrations; solving problems in Excel; computer workshop*

Introduction

The potential of information technology in the modern education system is determined by a wide range of human development (emotions, intelligence, worldview, independent creative and critical thinking, aesthetic consciousness, etc.). The issues of the developmental potential of information technology are increasingly attracting the attention of domestic psychologists and educators working on the concept of "electronic pedagogy", since they believe that electronic educational resources provide ample opportunities for developmental learning [6].

The use of electronic educational resources does not change the duration of training, and often requires more time, but provides the teacher with an opportunity to more deeply illuminate a particular theoretical issue. At the same time, their use helps students delve into those physical processes and phenomena in more detail, to study important theoretical issues that could not be studied without the use of interactive models.

The most significant of these differences can be seen in the study of physics, mathematics and computer science. Each discipline is characterized by its own approaches to the study of new material and its assimilation by students. Physics is an experimental science, the main approach to its study is the use of demonstration of physical phenomena or processes. The process of mastering new material in physics occurs from abstract thinking to theoretical generalization.

Mathematics - it is generally accepted that this is a theoretical and abstract science, therefore, when explaining new material, traditional approaches are used. In this case, the main role belongs to the teacher, who can communicate and prove the material himself. In the process of teaching mathematics, often, in order to save time, the research approach is not used, therefore, it is most appropriate to use electronic educational resources in the form of a "ready-made"

demonstration. The process of teaching computer science is focused on the individual learning capabilities of students.

Despite the differences in these educational sciences, each of them must have a common educational component - the development of research skills, which is realized through interdisciplinary connections between mathematics, physics and computer science lessons.

With the advent of computers in educational institutions, the teaching style began to change, and the project form of educational activity began to be used more and more. A computer with a special software package helps students conduct experiments, process the results, actually see the physical processes taking place with their graphic display during the experiment, and acquire the skill of reading graphic information.

This method has the following advantages over conventional measurement methods:

- the ability to instantly record the phenomena occurring and, as a consequence, obtain a large amount of experimental data;
- the presence of a computer program that processes the results of the experiment, relieves children of routine mathematical operations and presents the results of the experiment in a convenient form;
- the availability of multiple repetitions of the experiment with minimal time spent on routine operations for its implementation.

The ability of the computer to track and process a laboratory experiment allows you to intensify the educational process and use the freed up time for a detailed explanation of the observed phenomenon. The modularity of the course of new technologies allows you to form the content of the subject at the discretion of the teacher.

Performing laboratory work, solving experimental problems, observing physical phenomena outside the laboratory - all these models of research search activities will be relevant in the future life of the student, regardless of the chosen profession.

Information technologies of education enable the teacher to apply:

- an intelligent teaching system, which has such features as adaptation to the knowledge and characteristics of the student, flexibility of the learning process, selection of the optimal educational impact, determination of the causes of errors;
- instrumental authoring systems, which are based on the latest achievements in the field of artificial intelligence and are, of course, advanced for the development of applied computer programs aimed at a problem-oriented approach to learning;
- specialized computer training programs for knowledge control, pedagogical testing and organization of lecture support;
- automated teaching aids in the process of training specialists.

The effectiveness of using the latest information technologies in the educational process largely depends on the successful solution of methodological problems related to the information content and the method of using automated teaching systems in the educational process. There is a close relationship between existing teaching methods (pedagogical techniques) and the methodological content and pedagogical purpose of the software and methodological complex. Modern capabilities of new information technologies aimed at maximum unification, at the level of software and hardware, make it possible to create software and methodological training complexes as a set of educational fragments united by algorithmic means that set the learning trajectory.

Accompanying lecture material with dynamic images, high-quality static graphs, texts with various styles, sound is carried out with the help of author's information systems, helps the teacher in explaining this material.

Since the ultimate goal of the learning process is control and testing, which determine and scientifically measure the degree of assimilation of educational material and mastery of the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities, specialized author's information systems must support the following functionality:

- a wide range of methods for presenting tasks;
- a full range of methods for analyzing and entering answers;
- flexibility in the methods of setting grades, the level of students' academic achievements;
- collection and processing of individual and group statistical information on the results of control;
- the ability to work in a local area network for the purpose of automatically collecting information about the progress of control and its results from all computers simultaneously.

Nowadays, the computer has become an integral part of experimental scientific installations and theoretical developments. Since teaching methods are related to the methods of scientific knowledge, the computer should also be used in the educational process. This requires special training programs that allow you to practice algorithms for solving physical problems, model physical phenomena, that is, they serve to create a kind of physical laboratory into which you can "let" students for independent experimentation, allow you to demonstrate very subtle physical effects that were previously inaccessible for demonstration in the physics classroom.

Due to the use of computers that allow you to model and observe many phenomena, the possibilities of traditional physics practical training are significantly expanded.

The main task of the teacher is to make the acquired knowledge personally significant for the student. To do this, it is necessary to focus on increasing the independent work of schoolchildren in the organization of the educational process. In the activities of the teacher - the main figure in the educational process - the maximum role should be played by the work on organizing the cognitive activity of students, and not by communicating information to them. It is well known from the basics of didactics that only independent individual educational activity can lead to the formation of strong and deep knowledge, sustainable skills. In our opinion, the most important thing in teaching physics is that students understand the essence and causes of the phenomena that occur, and not just their external side. Therefore, methods of such teaching that would clearly show the connection between the observed phenomena and their theoretical description are relevant. These include demonstrations and laboratory work conducted in an appropriate manner using new information technologies. It is necessary to use systems that facilitate the perception of physical material simultaneously from the qualitative and quantitative side, allowing you to visualize the course of the process being studied, important experimental moments and its behavior in the environment of measured parameters. It is possible to implement computer technology of teaching only with the presence of an appropriate educational and methodological complex, as well as computer literacy of the teacher and students.

Computer literacy is a set of knowledge and skills that allows the teacher and students to use a computer as a teaching tool. The teacher and his students must have practical skills in handling a computer, know the general principles of its construction and functioning, understand the meaning, role and application of computer technology in various areas of human

activity. In addition to computer literacy, a teacher must have computer culture - a culture of complex use of electronic computing equipment in the educational process, skillfully determine the place and time of using computer technology in teaching.

The main pedagogical goals of using computer technology in teaching physics are the following:

- development of the creative potential of the student, his or her abilities for communicative actions, skills in experimental and research activities, culture of educational activities; increasing motivation for learning;
- intensification of all levels of the educational process, increasing its efficiency and quality;
- implementation of the social order caused by the informatization of modern society (training the user by means of computer technology).

The use of computer technology allows organizing independent cognitive work of students to study the phenomena of the surrounding reality. There are different options for organizing the work of students: performing research under the guidance and according to the instructions of the teacher; you can offer students to independently put forward hypotheses, and conduct the research according to the plan proposed by the teacher. An option is possible in which students themselves draw up a research plan, carry it out and draw conclusions. In this case, the reproductive method of teaching is replaced by independent acquisition of knowledge based on the implementation of experimental research activities, leading the student (with the appropriate methodology) to the independent discovery of the studied pattern.

Conclusion

Thus, the process of communicating ready-made knowledge and its experimental verification in the traditional methodology is replaced by experimental research activities.

Currently, there are a large number of works on various sections of physics, but not all the programs that we were able to get acquainted with have a convenient user interface, high-quality graphic design and sufficient methodological development. Many still have a DOS interface, although a graphic one is more convenient. The quality of dynamic graphics is of great importance. The use of poor-quality animation can lead to students having an incorrect idea of the ongoing process. Animation close to reality helps the student to better understand the phenomenon. A well-designed practical course promotes understanding of complex processes and phenomena, stimulates the cognitive interest of students.

Conclusion

In modern conditions, the problem of improving physics classrooms and creating equipped computer classes in order to increase the effectiveness of physics education is acute. Previously developed textbooks, teaching aids, programs are suitable only for fully equipped physics classrooms, but they cannot fully meet the training requirements. In this regard, it is advisable to use computer technologies in the process of teaching physics and, in particular, in setting up a physical experiment. Today, there are many educational programs for modeling a physical experiment on computers. The choice of pedagogical software is huge and an ordinary teacher gets lost in the sea of information dumped on him by manufacturers. It is necessary to acquaint the physics teacher with ready-made computer products that can help him in the classroom.

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